

Delphi consensus study – Round 1

We thank you for having accepted to contribute to this study and welcome you to this first round. During this round, you are to help define overall treatment goals and intermediary goals (endpoints), and suggest underlying theory models we could rely on to achieve them (eg. social learning theory, cognitive learning theory, theory of reason or action, behaviourism). This round includes 20 questions. They are organized in six sections. Completing the form requires approximately 30-45 minutes.

1. Please provide your studyID (Q1)

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All your answers are made anonymous. It is however important to provide your studyID for us to link your responses through different rounds.

We thank you again for the interest in this topic and for your important contribution in finding adapted solutions for ageing drivers.

Developing definitions of treatment goals

2. List up to three treatment goals that you consider as most important to achieve when addressing the problem of driving cessation with ageing people ? (Q2)

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Feel free to come back to this question once you have finished the form.

Assessing the relevance of endpoints

Relying on Prochaska and DiClemente's transtheoretical model to define stages of changes and Liddle & al's (2008) adaptation to driving cessation, we defined four endpoints. We would like you to let us know whether you consider these endpoints as relevant or not. To be completely relevant, they need to correspond to important endpoints you would expect, they need to refer to clinical relevant time points, they need to relate to phases through which most or all patients need to go through, and they need to be correctly formulated.

Assessing the relevance of each endpoint

Please rate each endpoint from irrelevant to completely relevant on the following numerical rating scales.

3. Endpoint 1: Being aware of advantages of driving cessation and personal resources (Q3)

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

4. Endpoint 2: Owning the decision of transition (Q4)

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

5. Endpoint 3: Choosing adapted alternatives (Q5)

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

6. Endpoint 4: Acknowledging changes are integrated (Q6)

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

7. If you found any of the endpoints inadequate (value < 6), please explain why and provide suggestions or alternatives. (Q7)

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- 8. **Can you think of any other important endpoints that need to be considered in this intervention (before, during or after) ? If so, could you briefly describe it and suggest a labeling? (Q8)**

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Endpoint 1 : Being aware of advantages of driving cessation and personal resources

This marks the end of the phase during which patients are confronted by the reality of their health condition and the difficulties this might lead to. It is the phase during which patients become aware that driving is no longer possible. The decision to cease driving shifts from an imposed external constraint to self-responsibility. People see the advantage of finding alternative mode of transport. It is therefore also the phase during which they can move their focus from their deficits to those of advantages in changes and highlight their resources thereby making the idea of change possible.

- 9. **Please list up to three underlying theory models / approaches you would rely on to have patients become aware of advantages of driving cessation ? (Q9)**

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- 10. **Please list up to three underlying theory models / approaches you would rely on to have patients become aware of their personal resources ? (Q10)**

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Endpoint 2 : Owing the decision of transition

This endpoint marks the end of the phase during which patients make the decision of transition their own. We are moving from the phase of recognizing the need to take decisions to the phase of taking the decisions. Different procedures can help patients go through this important step that will strengthen their involvement in therapy.

11. Please list up to three underlying theory models / approaches that you would rely on to help patients own the decision of driving cessation and transport transfer. (Q11)

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Endpoint 3 : Choosing adapted alternatives

This endpoint marks the end of the phase during which different changes are explored and tested with the patient and adapted alternatives are chosen. The aim is for the patient to make satisfying choices for adapted alternatives.

Provide a short description of what you would mean by each of the following concepts ?

12. Changes in residency or places of destination (Q12)

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13. Changes in transport (Q13)

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14. Changes in occupation (Q14)

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15. Changes in social interactions (Q15)

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16. Changes in emotional attachments (Q16)

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17. Apart from the five types of changes suggested above, can you think of any other type of change that could be explored? If so, please provide a brief description. (Q17)

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18. What approach(es) would you rely on to make sure that the proposed solutions are adapted? (Q18)

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Endpoint 4 : Acknowledging changes are integrated

This endpoint marks the end of the phase during which patients integrate changes in behavior. This longer phase consists of a follow-up period (maximum 6 months) during which solutions are adjusted and patients integrate new habits through repetition. There is also a progressive decrease in assistance as patients recover their autonomy in choosing strategies to get to the places they want to.

19. List up to three approaches you would rely on to have patients integrate changes? (Q19)

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20. List up to three approaches you would rely on to have patients develop their autonomy in their ability to enhance changes in mobility? (Q20)

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End of Round 1

You have answered the last question. You will be invited for the next round on January 26th. Feel free to move back and forth to revise your answers. Once you are satisfied with all your answers, press the submit button on this page.

